

Contributi/4

Casuietry in Action

Individuals' Challenge to Eugenic Collectivism as Seen in Court Cases in Japan

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The 1948 Eugenic Protection Law (Yūsei hogo hō) in Japan ushered in a collectivist, utilitarian, generalized paradigm in Japanese social life and jurisprudence. The individual, whether as unwanted child, diseased adult, or social inferior, was aborted, sterilized, quarantined, and otherwise removed from the collective under ideological cover of eugenics and other such totalizing schemes. However, in court cases in recent years, the Japanese authorities have begun to look again, even for the first time, at the individuals who were harmed and disregarded in the eugenic postwar. In this essay, I rely on a July, 2024 Japanese Supreme Court ruling, and other recent court cases, to track «casuistry in action» that is, the irrepressible individual in court cases and social life and the contingency, disruptive to all totalizing ideologies, which the individual always brings. I understand the casuistry of recent court cases in Japan to be a victory for contingency and a challenge to eugenics and the set pattern of laws.

1. Introduction

On July 3, 2024, the Japanese Supreme Court issued several rulings on the now-notorious Eugenic Protection Law (Yūsei hogo hō), passed in 1948 under the American Occupation (and under American pressure) and amended several times until it was finally abolished in 1996¹. The rulings were historic. They overturned previous Supreme Court and lower court rulings upholding the forced sterilizations, forced abortions, and other grave human rights abuses which the Eugenic Protection Law had enabled and even encouraged. The July, 2024 rulings also overturned previous rulings denying compensation to Eugenic Protection Law victims based on statute of limitations laws. Even more

¹Y. Okada, *Yūsei hogo hō no jidai wo ikiru: aru seishinkai no sengoshi*, Tokyo 2024, pp. 147-168.

important, the July, 2024 Supreme Court rulings declared unconstitutional the Eugenic Protection Law and the abuses carried out in that law's name.

The July, 2024 rulings display the power of a case – that is, of casuistry, of moral reasoning grounded in empirical fact – to disrupt the generalized aspects of human existence². They remind us that casuistry is the irruption of the individual within the general, the particular's complication and rejection of the totalizing generic. This is doubly true when court cases involve eugenics practices, as eugenics is the privileging of the race, the social grouping, the genetic line, or some other individual-eclipsing (even-eradicating) collective or process. Cases involving individuals who have suffered in body or soul because of eugenics ideologies – premised on the subsumption of the individual to the group – amplify the power of casuistry by allowing the individual to re-emerge both within the eyes of the law and the eugenic averaging of the masses. The July, 2024 court rulings in Japan are also triply disruptive. They not only re-present the individual case within the legal framework (casuistry) and the eugenic whole, but also reject eugenics as an ideology. For these reasons, the July rulings mark a turning point in Japanese legal history.

In this essay, I examine this triply-disruptive power of the July, 2024 Japanese Supreme Court rulings from three angles. First, I examine the nature of eugenics to see how ideas about the relationship between the individual and the state (and society) were challenged by the July, 2024 rulings, which interjected the lived experience of the individual into jurisprudential discourse in a classically casuistic way. Second, I examine the July, 2024 rulings from a legal philosophical standpoint, finding that the tension between the general and the specific found in all legislation (and Japan is no exception) has changed as the individual has gained more prominence in Japanese jurisprudence over time since the early days of the American Occupation of the Japanese archipelago. Third, I view the July, 2024 rulings as a casuistic victory for contingency, a reminder that law's complement is always law's exception³.

Eugenics in Japan, as elsewhere, has often pitted the person against the group, the mother against the child, the particular against the collective, the race against the human person. But above all else, eugenics is an attempt to overcome contingency through genetic collectivism, to eliminate uncontrolled change and tame time by relegating genetic variation to a subordinate role vis-à-vis curated

² H. Rashdall, *The Limits of Casuistry*, «International Journal of Ethics», 4, 4, 1984, p. 463; R. da Silva Ehalt, *Theology in the Dark: The Missionary Casuistry of Japan Jesuits and Dominicans during the Tokugawa Persecution (1616-1622)*, in Manuel Bastias Saavedra (ed.), *Norms beyond Empire: Law-Making and Local Normativities in Iberian Asia, 1500-1800*. Leiden 2022, pp. 252, 263-264; P. Meadows, *The Semiotic of Kenneth Burke*, «Philosophy and Phenomenology Research», 18, 1, 1957, pp. 86-87; J. W. Lango, *The Ethics of Armed Conflict: A Cosmopolitan Just War Theory*. Edinburgh 2014, pp. 51-57; and H. L. Stewart, *The Need for a Modern Casuistry*, «International Journal of Ethics», 24, 4, 1914, pp. 379, 399.

³ See C. Ginzburg, and L. Biasiori (eds.), *A Historical Approach to Casuistry: Norms and Exceptions in a Comparative Perspective*, London 2019, and P. Griseri, *In Defence of Principles? A Response to Lurie and Albin*, «Journal of Business Ethics», 83, 2008, pp. 615-625.

racial stocks. Over and against this, the appearance of new combinations of the human genome – that is, babies – and the reality of disease and other genetic imperfections demand that we pay attention to individuals over collectives. Eugenics is an ideal, and also a mirage. There are no perfect people or perfect races. The individual will never be subsumed to the genetic collective, in practice or in law. In July of 2024, the Japanese Supreme Court struck a blow for the case and the individual, as well as for the dignity of the human person contra the eugenic paradigm.

2. First Disruption: Eugenics

The history of eugenics in Japan parallels the history of eugenics in the United States and elsewhere in the West, although this parallelism unfolded in a very different biopolitical context⁴. While both Japan and the West followed a eugenics path roughly as laid out by Francis Galton (1822-1911) in his definition of eugenics, there are big differences⁵. In the United States, for example, eugenics has often been a fundamentally racist and racist ideology, according to which the strength of a given race must be preserved by selecting in favor of superior genes⁶. The preservation of white prerogatives, and the concomitant constraining of non-white breeding, form the iron frame for much of American eugenics. Even Black American philosopher W.E.B. Dubois (1868-1963) reflected the racist temperament of American eugenics in arguing that the «Talented Tenth» of Black Americans should carry forward and enhance the Black race⁷. But Dubois' attempts at Black uplift must be understood to have taken place in an environment of virulent white supremacy, much of it suffused

⁴ S. Sakamoto, *Josei no kenri kara mita dataizai to yūsei hogo hō, soshite botai hogo hō*, «Higashi Ajia Kenkyū», 63, 2015, pp. 33-34; I. Konuma, *Yūsei shisō to jinken: yūsei hogo hō no keizaiteki jōkō ni kansuru ichikōsatsu*, «Hikaku Nihongaku Kyōiku Kenkyū Bumon Kenkyū Nenpō», 14, 2018, p. 169; T. Norgren, *Abortion before Birth Control: The Politics of Reproduction in Postwar Japan*. Princeton 2001; K. Kabe, *Seiiku genkai no seimei rinri*, «Daiyonjūkai Shūsankigaku Shinpojiumu Sharokushū», 2022, pp. 18-22, and Y. Matsubara, *Kagakushi nyūmon: Yūsei hogo hō no rekishizō no saktō*, «Kagakushi Kenkyū», 41, 2002, pp. 104-105.

⁵ «Eugenics is the science which deals with all influences that improve the inborn qualities of a race; also with those that develop them to the utmost advantage». F. Galton, *Eugenics: Its Definition, Scope, and Aims*, «American Journal of Sociology», 10, 1, 1904, p. 1. See also A. Pichot, *The Pure Society: From Darwin to Hitler*. New York, 2009, tr. D. Fernbach; and T. Yokoyama, *Nihon ga yūsei shakai ni naru made: kagaku keimō, medeia, seishoku no seiji*. Tokyo 2015.

⁶ I. Konuma, *Yūsei shisō to jinken*, pp. 168-169; F. Galton, *Inquiries into Human Faculty and Its Development*. New York 1883; E. J. Larson, *Sex, Race, and Science: Eugenics in the Deep South*. Baltimore, MD 1995; E. Black, *War against the Weak: Eugenics and America's Campaign to Create a Master Race*, Washington DC 2003; S. Kühn, *The Nazi Connection: Eugenics, American Racism, and German National Socialism*. New York 1994; C. Boeckmann, *A Question of Character: Scientific Racism and the Genres of American Fiction, 1892-1912*, Tuscaloosa 2000; and N. Rafter, *Earnest A. Hooton and the Biological Tradition in American Criminology*, «Criminology», 42, 3, 2004, pp. 754-756.

⁷ K. Castles, *Review of Unnatural Selections: Eugenics in American Modernism and the Harlem Renaissance*, by Daylanne K. English, «Journal of Southern History», 71, 3, 2005, pp. 727-728; D. Chinitz, *The New Harlem Renaissance Studies*, «Modernism/Modernity», 13, 2, 2006, p. 380.

with eugenicist thought. That key United States Supreme Court decisions on eugenics (typified by the 1927 ruling in *Buck v. Bell*) coincided with a lynching epidemic and crackdowns on non-white immigration (e.g., the Johnson-Reed Act of 1924) is indicative of the socio-legal context within which American eugenics developed⁸.

In Japan, by contrast, while the health of the Japanese people as a whole was often a eugenicist aim, competition with other races was a secondary eugenics aim. There were, to be sure, those in Japan such as Ikeda Ringi (aka Ikeda Shigenori) (1892-1966), who advocated for a collectivist Japanese race on the prewar German model and argued in favor of what Ikeda termed the «genetic society» (*yūsei shakai*)⁹. But this was an outlying view, even considering that the National Eugenic Law in Japan, introduced in 1940, was written in imitation of the infamous 1933 eugenics law in Germany¹⁰. Early Japanese eugenics hewed much closer to the Malthusian side of the ideology, which stressed the control of population as a numerical, and not so much a racial-quality, concern¹¹. Japan faced a pressing social problem in the late nineteenth and twentieth centuries, namely, a sudden increase in population¹². Many Japanese emigrated overseas as a way, partly, of escaping famine and poverty at home, ills which many in Japan and elsewhere attributed to overpopulation¹³. Many Japanese policymakers were in favor of restricting Japan's population to prevent such social ills in Japan, and also as a way of circumscribing or circumventing the international trouble that came when the Japanese poor went to live abroad in large numbers. Hence the Malthusian tenor to much of Japanese eugenics.

Another early aspect of Japanese eugenics was therapeutic. Japan's history of care for leprosy patients and sufferers of other diseases exemplifies the non-Western strands of eugenic thought in Japan¹⁴. In pre-Meiji Japan, for instance, lepers (*raisha*), or those with what is now known as Hansen's disease, enjoyed

⁸ P. A. Lombardo, *Three Generations, No Imbeciles: Eugenics, the Supreme Court, and Buck v. Bell*. Baltimore 2008; E. M. Beck, *Judge Lynch Denied: Combating Mob Violence in the American South, 1877-1950*, «Southern Cultures», 21, 2, 2015, pp. 117-139; S. X. Lu, *The Making of Japanese Settler Colonialism: Malthusianism and Trans-Pacific Migration, 1868-1961*. Cambridge 2019; S. C. Smith, *Buck as (Anti) Canon: The Misuse of Eugenics Rhetoric in Selective-Abortion Jurisprudence and the Dangers for Tort Law*, «American University Law Review», 73, 2023, pp. 449-505; M. M. Ngai, *The Architecture of Race in American Immigration Law: A Reexamination of the Immigration Act of 1924*, «Journal of American History», 86, 1, 1999, pp. 67-92; and R. W. Rydell, *The Proximity of the Past: Eugenics in American Culture*, «Modern Intellectual History», 7, 3, 2010, pp. 667-678.

⁹ R. Ikeda, *Shidōsha minzoku no yūseigakuteki ishin*. Osaka 1942, pp. 58-62; see also Y. Fujino, *Nihon fashizumu to yūsei shisō*, Kyoto 1998, pp. 84-91.

¹⁰ T. Yokoyama, *Yūseigakushi ni okeru Nihon minzoku eisei gakkai no ichi*, «Nihon Kenkō Gakkai Shi», 86, 5, 2020, pp. 197-208.

¹¹ S. Ogawa, *Yūsei hogo hō no mondaiten ni tsuite*, in «Minzoku Eisei», 30, 1, 1964, p. 15.

¹² S. Otsubo, *Globalizing Reproductive Politics: Sanger's Legacy in Japan*, «Journal of the Gilded Age and Progressive Era», 17, 4, 2018, p. 728.

¹³ S. X. Lu, *The Making of Japanese Settler Colonialism*.

¹⁴ T. Furui and M. Furui, *Nijū seiki de owaranakatta yūsei shisō: shōgai to tomo ni ikiru jinsei ga hitsuzen no jidai ni*, «Ōsaka Kawasaki Rihabiriteishon Daigaku Kiyō», 15, 2021, pp. 25-27.

a degree of societal freedom higher in many cases than lepers in Western countries¹⁵. Even as eugenics ideology began to filter into Japan, many Japanese doctors and philanthropists continued to insist on treating Hansen's disease sufferers humanely. Ogasawara Noboru (1888-1970), for example, writes researcher Setoguchi Yūji, relied on his own clinical experience and the teachings of his father to conclude that «leprosy is not contagious» (*rai wa utsuranai*)¹⁶. If leprosy is not contagious, and if it also cannot be passed along genetically, then the eugenics argument in favor of sacrificing the individual for the sake of the collective breaks down. In other words, in Japan there was a tradition of maintaining the dignity of the individual against the impulse to sacrifice the individual for the sake of the collective. Had this mindset prevailed, there would have been no later court cases in a post-eugenics Japan in which the individual re-emerged into social view – after having been erased from society in the name of eugenics – via the operations of casuistry.

In the late nineteenth and twentieth centuries, however, and especially as eugenics ideology took root, the Japanese government's and medical establishment's approach to leprosy in many ways not only mirrored Western practices, but went beyond them. Collectivism became the norm. Physician Gotō Masafumi (1826-1895), for instance, persuaded the Japanese government to back his plan to set up «treatment centers» for lepers¹⁷. Gotō's pleas to the central government in Tokyo eventually persuaded government officials to fund his Kihai Hospital¹⁸. This was part of a global movement at the time in favor of treatments for leprosy, part of the European-American, and later Japanese, optimism that «civilization» could be brought to parts of the world less «enlightened» than others¹⁹. This eugenics thought and the anti-individual practices it engendered have been revealed in more recent cases in Japan. In May of 2001, for instance, the Kumamoto District Court in southwestern Honshu found that more than 1,400 eugenics surgeries (*yūsei shujutsu*) had been performed between 1949 (a year after the implementation of the Eugenic Protection Law) and 1996 (when the Eugenic Protection Law was repealed) on the grounds that those being operated on were Hansen's disease patients, and that more than 3,000 abortions were carried out during the same period for the same reason²⁰. Moreover, the same court recognized that Hansen's disease patients living in forced quarantine in special sanatoria (*ryōyōjo*) were forced to undergo sterilization operations in

¹⁵ S. L. Burns, *Kingdom of the Sick: A History of Leprosy and Japan*. Honolulu, 2019.

¹⁶ Y. Setoguchi, *Yūsei hogo hō ka de umareta Hansenbyō kanja no kodomotachi: sono jinbutsushiteki kōsatsu no tame no jobiteki kenkyū*, «Nayoro Shiritsu Daigaku Shakaifukushi Gakka Kenkyū Kiyō», 1, 2012, p. 26.

¹⁷ S. L. Burns, *Kingdom of the Sick*, pp. 74-79.

¹⁸ S. L. Burns, *Kingdom of the Sick*, p. 81.

¹⁹ S. L. Burns, *Kingdom of the Sick*, pp. 102-117.

²⁰ Y. Nishimura, *Yūsei hogo hō to Hansenbyō: yūsei hogo hō ka de okonawareta Hansenbyō kanja ni taisuru funin shujutsu*, «Gunma Daigaku Shakai Jōhō Gakubu Kenkyū Ronshū», 31, 2024, p. 49.

order to live together with their spouses in those facilities²¹. On March 27, 1996, a bill passed unanimously in the Japanese Diet directing that Hansen's disease no longer be listed under the purview of the Eugenics Protection Law²². The Kumamoto decision issued five years later reflects the painful legacy of eugenics ideology as deployed in Japan against lepers. But it is also testament to the power of casuistry. This power of casuistry is the victory, however temporary, of the individual (human person or case) over the (racialist or legal) collective, even when the collective is privileged on putatively hygienic grounds.

The individual-versus-collective paradigm which the 2001 Kumamoto case foregrounds can be detected throughout the eugenic history of Japan. A good example is given by a physician named Mitsuda Kensuke (1876-1974). Researcher Nishimura Yoshiko writes that Dr. Mitsuda is widely understood to have performed the first sterilization operation carried out in Japan on a Hansen's disease patient, in April of 1915²³. Nakamura Nozomu (1875-1964), the head of the Hygienics Bureau (Eisei kyoku) of the Japanese Home Ministry at the time, urged Dr. Mitsuda to obtain consent forms from patients in order to avoid being charged with a crime for such actions²⁴. In this way, Nakamura accepted the eugenics practices of Dr. Mitsuda while appearing, in a legalistic way, to emphasize the primacy of the individual over the genetic group. In light of later casuistry undertaken by the Japanese courts, which allowed judges to discern the individual through the obscuring screen of the eugenics collective, we can see that the Japanese government long operated in the liminal space between insisting on patient consent in the particular and overriding the meaning of consent at the level of legislation and policy. For instance, the Japanese government provided guidance for doctors performing vasectomies and other sterilization procedures on male lepers, and insisted on sterilization as a condition of cohabitating with wives at government-run Hansen's patient colonies²⁵. This legal liminality grows even more complicated when the state, operating under eugenic assumptions, used abortions to root out unwanted genes when sterilization could not be performed in time. Some Hansen's disease patients were forced to undergo abortions in up to the ninth month of pregnancy, and many others underwent forced abortions in the seventh and eighth months of gestation²⁶.

The liminal, brackish nature of eugenics in Japan, wherein the individual was granted at least nominal autonomy even as the prerogatives of the collective (the race, the state, the «Japanese people») were prioritized, was ended abruptly in the immediate postwar. When the Americans and their allies defeated Japan

²¹ Y. Nishimura, *Yūsei hogo hō to Hansenbyō*, p. 49; K. Toshimitsu, *Yūsei hogo hō no moto de no kyōsei funin shujutsu to kōbunsho*, «Ritsumeikan Seizongaku Kenkyū», 3, 2019, p. 129.

²² K. Iida, *Human Rights and Sexual Abuse: The Impact of International Human Rights Law on Japan*, «Human Rights Quarterly», 26, 2, 2004, p. 439.

²³ Y. Nishimura, *Yūsei hogo hō to Hansenbyō*, p. 50

²⁴ Y. Nishimura, *Yūsei hogo hō to Hansenbyō*, p. 50

²⁵ Y. Nishimura, *Yūsei hogo hō to Hansenbyō*, pp. 51, 55-59

²⁶ Y. Aoki, *Hansenbyō ryōyōjo nyūshosha noshintai shōgai: Setouchi san en nyūshosha no jittai chōsa niyoru kenkyū*, «Nihon Kōshū Eisei Zasshi», 51, 9, 2004, p. 749.

in 1945, the Americans dominated the legal life of the country they were occupying, and in this way used the law as a conduit for Western eugenics – which countenanced little mercy for individuals – to rise in Japan. The high, or low, point of the American eugenic takeover of Japan came in 1948. In that year the Japanese Diet, acting under similar Occupation pressure as had been applied when the new American-authored constitution came into effect the year before, passed the Eugenic Protection Law²⁷.

On the surface, at the level of public discourse and parliamentary procedure, the eugenic initiative appeared to be entirely homegrown. On August 28, 1947, House of Councillors members Fukuda Masako (1912-1975), Katō Shizue (1897-2001), and Ōta Tenrei (1900-1985), all members of the Japan Socialist Party, introduced a draft eugenics protection bill to the upper house of the Diet.²⁸ Researcher Kevin Doak points out that «Inoue Natsue [(1898-1980)], head of the Japan Nurses Association [and also a member of the House of Councilors], [...] argued that, given widespread poverty in Japan, abortion was a necessary evil to enable women to have ‘an enjoyable family life’»²⁹. Lawmaker and future Supreme Court Chief Justice of Japan and judge on the International Court of Justice Tanaka Kōtarō (1890-1974), in a House of Councillors address on May 14, 1949, denounced the «ghastly methods,» namely, abortion, that were being used in Japan for purposes of population control³⁰. In a 1948 book titled *Explaining the Eugenic Protection Law* (*Yūsei hogo hō kaisetsu*), House of Councilors member Taniguchi Yasaburō (1883-1963), a leading voice in the call for population control in occupied Japan, wrote that feeding Japan’s postwar population among the ruin the war had wrought on Japan was a pressing concern necessitating curtailing further increases in population³¹. It would appear that the eugenics push in postwar Japan was a native Japanese initiative.

However, Taniguchi framed his call for population control in language very similar to that which Margaret Sanger (1879-1966), who had visited Japan in 1922 on the invitation of Katō Shizue, had used in explaining the necessity of limiting the number of non-white births in the United States³². Taniguchi lamented that while those in «superior households» (*yūshūsha no katei*) were properly practicing birth control, those of «low ability and status, that is, the

²⁷ T. Norgren, *Abortion before Birth Control*, pp. 69-76.

²⁸ Ōta later distanced himself from the «dysgenic» arguments implicit in the original eugenics discourse. See K. Hiroshima, *Sengo Nihon jinkō seisakushi kara kangaeru*, «Nihon Kenkō Gakkaishi», 86, 5, 2020, pp. 232-233. See also Y. Nishimura, *Yūsei hogo hō to Hansenyō*, p. 54; and A. Takeuchi-Demirci, *Contraceptive Diplomacy: Reproductive Politics and Imperial Ambitions in the United States and Japan*, Stanford 2018, pp. 154-159.

²⁹ K. Doak, *Tanaka Kōtarō and World Law: Rethinking the Natural Law Order outside the West*, Cham 2019, p. 78; see also N. Inoue, *Waga mae ni michi wa hiraku: Inoue Natsue jijoden*. Tokyo 1973.

³⁰ K. Doak, *Tanaka Kōtarō and World Law*, p. 78.

³¹ Y. Nishimura, *Yūsei hogo hō to Hansenyō*, p. 54, citing Y. Taniguchi and M. Fukuda, *Yūsei hogo hō kaisetsu*, Tokyo 1948; see also K. Hiroshima, *Sengo Nihon jinkō seisakushi kara kangaeru*, p. 232.

³² A. Takeuchi-Demirci, *Contraceptive Diplomacy*, 35-40; see also S. Ogawa, *Yūsei hogo hō no mondaiten ni tsuite*, «Minzoku Eisei», 30, 1, 1964, p. 15.

inferior» (*retsuakusha sunawachi teinōsha teikakusha*) were virtually indifferent to birth control, with the result that the births of the superior people were reduced while those of the inferior were ever increasing¹. Left unchecked, Taniguchi and his co-author Fukuda Masako lamented, the people of Japan as a whole would begin to appear of lower quality, much like an untended field in which no care had been taken to remove the weeds from amid the crops². With this, Taniguchi and Fukuda continued, it was «beyond apparent» (*hi wo miru yori akiraka de aru*) that the Japanese race would enter into a state of «dysgenic» (*gyakutōta*) decline³. The «weeds» analogy, many readers will recognize, was redolent of Sanger's infamous eugenic views about those whom she considered racially inferior⁴.

Much closer behind the scenes than Sanger to this eugenic talk in postwar Japan was Brigadier General Crawford Fountain Sams (1902-1994), who was pushing Japan to control its population by abortion and other means⁵. Sams was the head of the Public Health and Welfare (*Kōshū eisei fukushi kyoku*) under the ultimate direction of the Supreme Commander for the Allied Powers (SCAP), General Douglas MacArthur (1880-1964), and as such had tremendous power to influence and direct infection disease countermeasures, public sexuality, and abortion policy in Japan⁶. With the occupation of Japan by the Americans, Japanese eugenics, once a complex set of native and foreign practices and ideas, was subordinated to American interests⁷. In a very American way, initiatives such as strengthening the Japanese racial stock through selective breeding (accomplished in many cases by elective abortion) and controlling the Japanese population as a way to avoid overly burdening the American occupiers with the duty to provide for the Japanese people were folded, by Japanese intellectuals and with the help of American censors, into discourse about ideal family sizes, equality of the sexes, and individual autonomy⁸. By contrast, Okinawa, which was under the direct control of the United States in the form of the U.S. Civil

¹ Y. Nishimura, *Yūsei hogo hō to Hansenbyō*, p. 54; see also Y. Nihei, *Ningen no kaizō*, Tokyo 1949, p. 108.

² Y. Nishimura, *Yūsei hogo hō to Hansenbyō*, p. 54.

³ Y. Nishimura, *Yūsei hogo hō to Hansenbyō*, p. 54.

⁴ L. Gershon, *Margaret Sanger's Eugenics Defense*, in «JSTOR Daily», 18, 2015; see also H. Olson, H. Cummings, and J. H. Wigmore, *The Loeb-Leopold Case (Concluded): A Symposium of Comments from the Legal Profession*, «Journal of the American Institute of Criminal Law and Criminology», 15, 3, 1924, p. 404.

⁵ K. Doak, *Tanaka Kōtarō and World Law*, p. 77; see also A. Takeuchi-Demirci, *Contraceptive Diplomacy*, pp. 121-126.

⁶ T. Chazono, *Panpan towa dare nanoka: kyacchi toiu senryōki no seibōryoku to GI tonō shinmitsusei*, Tokyo 2014, pp. 222-239.

⁷ Y. Fujime, *Sei no rekishigaku: kōshō seido, dataizai taisei kara Baishun bōshi hō, Yūsei hogo hō taisei e*, Tokyo 1997, pp. 356-377.

⁸ S. Sakamoto, *Josei no kenri kara mita dataizai to yūsei hogo hō, soshite botai hogo hō*, «Higashi Ajia Kenkyū», 63, 2015, p. 35; see also S. Ogawa, *Yūsei hogo hō no mondaiten ni tsuite*, 17; J. Mutsuro, *Hō no naka no danjo fubyōdō: Baishun bōshi hō, Yūsei hogo hō, Kōshitsu tenpan*, Tokyo 1994, pp. 49-94; E. Akiba, *'Hito' no hajimari wo meguru shinri no kōsatsu*, Tokyo 2010, pp. 50-56; and A. Tsuge, *Seishoku kanri no sengo: Yūsei hogo hō seiritsu mae no chūzetsu to shutai wo megutte*, in H. Tsuboi (ed.), *Jendā to seiseiji: sengo Nihon wo yomikaeru*, Kyoto 2019.

Administration of the Ryukyu Islands, lacked a pliant front operation in the form of the Japanese government. American-controlled Okinawa blocked the implementation of the Eugenic Protection Law. The later introduction of more American-style eugenics programs, such as under the auspices of the International Planned Parenthood Federation, increased abortion mentality in Okinawa, but Okinawa under direct American rule followed a separate postwar eugenics path⁹.

Eugenic thought in Japan, including Okinawa, goes back much earlier than the American Occupation, of course, with roots in the Bluestocking movement of female intellectuals and the big societal changes of Taishō Democracy in the 1920s¹⁰. But while there were eugenics laws in place prior to 1945, such as the Kokumin yūsei hō (National citizens' eugenics law) passed in 1940 under the Konoe Fumimaro (1891-1945) cabinet, and the related Kokumin tairyoku hō (National citizens' physical strength law) (also 1940), these laws were aimed mainly at strengthening Japanese bodies for mobilization in war and against infectious disease (such as tuberculosis)¹¹. As researcher Matsubara Yōko makes clear, the postwar implementation of sterilization (*danshu*) policies at levels beyond those of the prewar and wartime years in Japan was a feature of the postwar Eugenic Protection Law¹². Matsubara understands lawmaker Taniguchi Yasuburō's focus on both the loosening of restrictions on abortion and the strengthening of policies in favor of implementing sterilization surgeries as a package concept, with the revisions to the Eugenic Protection Law in 1949 (allowing abortion on grounds of economic hardship) and 1952 (abolishing the practice of conducting investigations into abortion circumstances, thereby making abortion available virtually on-demand), as consistent with the importance which postwar policymakers and physicians, operating under the watchful gaze of their American overlords, placed on sterilization practices¹³. Matsubara's analysis dovetails with the overall stated purpose of the Eugenic Protection Law, which was to prevent the «birth of inferior descendants»¹⁴. On a slightly wider, or more cynical, reading, the same language can be interpreted

⁹ K. Sawada, *Shushhōryoku to kazoku ni miru Okinawa: shūhenka sareta jinkō, seishoku wo meguru seiji*, «Shakaigaku Hyōron», 67, 4, 2016, pp. 404-406.

¹⁰ Y. Sono, *Yūsei shisō no shakaishi josetsu: Meiji ikō no Nihon shakai wo rei ni*, «Ningenkagaku Kyōsei Shakaigaku», 4, 2004, pp. 44-51; V. Mackie, *Gender and Modernity in Japan's 'Long Twentieth Century'*, «Journal of Women's History», 25, 3, 2013, pp. 68-71.

¹¹ T. Furui T. and M. Furui M. *Nijū seiki de owaranakatta yūsei shisō*, p. 30; S. Sakamoto, *Josei no kenri kara mita dataizai to yūsei hogo hō*, pp. 34-35; see also Y. Matsubara, *Nihon: sengo no Yūsei hogo hō toiu na no danshu hō*, in Y. Yonemoto, Y. Matsubara, J. Nudeshima, and Y. Ichinokawa, *Yūseigaku to ningen shakai: seimeikagaku no seiki wa doko he mukau noka*. Tokyo 2000, pp. 176-183.

¹² Y. Matsubara, *Kagakushi nyūmon*, p. 105.

¹³ Y. Matsubara, *Kagakushi nyūmon*, pp. 105-106.

¹⁴ M. Morioka, *Yūsei hogo hō kaisei wo meguru seimei rinri*, «Nihon Kenkyū: Kokusai Nihon Bunka Sentā Kiyō», 16, 1997, p. 211; M. Aoi, *Reonsetsu: kyū Yūsei hogo hō no ikensei oyobi sono moto de yūsei shujutsu wo uketa higaisha e no kyūsai rippō fusonzai no ikensei narabini kokka baishō hō jō no ihōsei ni tsuite*, «Gakushūin Hōmu Kenkyū», 13, 2019, pp. 6-7.

as a clandestine Washington strategy to weaken the Japanese, as a race, in a way calculated to protect long-term American interests in East Asia.

And yet, while public intellectuals (working in a regime of strict American censorship) lauded the individual in postwar Japan as the foundation of American-style liberal democracy, eugenics belied this talk by keeping biopolitics at the top of the state's list of priorities¹⁵. Under the guidance of, in part, Taniguchi Masaharu (1893-1985) and his Seichō no Ie religious group, and especially the political federation that that group headed, opposition to abortion became a political movement from the 1960s and into the 1970s¹⁶. That many within Japan were in favor of sterilizing some Japanese people on eugenicist grounds should be understood, in one sense, as part of a global consensus, in some quarters at least, that sterilization in particular and eugenics in general was essential to achieving a utilitarian vision of the greatest good for the greatest number (excluding, of course, those who had been sterilized, aborted, or otherwise harmed in the name of eugenics). But this global argument becomes much more difficult to make when one considers that American racists such as Senator Theodore Bilbo (1877-1947) of Mississippi advised Gen. MacArthur that «all Japanese» should be sterilized¹⁷. Others shared Senator Bilbo's sentiments¹⁸. Japanese intellectuals and pundits may have thought that the eugenics they were advocating was still about Malthusian population control or even improving the Japanese racial stock, but things looked very different from the racist-tinged American perspective.

In a truly casuistic way, however, the attempts by postwar eugenicists, both American and Japanese, to impose a biopolitical regime on the entire Japanese population ran continuously up against the complicating figure of the individual. No matter how skillfully the postwar eugenic paradigm in Japan was justified in public discourse, no matter how necessary the paradigm was said to be in terms of politics and geopolitics, and no matter how much opposition the paradigm encountered in the form of mass political mobilization, such as by Taniguchi Masaharu and his followers, it was the individual who formed the only counter to the eugenic totalization, both in society and in law. Consider the forced sterilization cases taken up in the July, 2024 Supreme Court rulings. Clauses three, four, and twelve of the 1948 Eugenic Protection Law, which stipulate that the consent of the patient is not necessary in sterilization procedures, were used frequently to justify forced sterilization operations on those deemed genetically

¹⁵ M. Sekino, *Daigokai: Tōkyō saiban kenkyūkai, 'Nihonjin wo kuruwaseta sennō kōsaku "WGIP": sono mokuteki to shisōteki genryū: soshite damasareru Nihonjingawa no yōin to kongo e no kyōkun'*, «Hikaku Hōsei Kenkyū», 39, 2016, pp. 163-197; S. Takahashi, *'Nihon wo kaitai suru' sensō purōpaganda no genzai: WGIP no genryū wo saguru*, Tokyo 2016; S. Takahashi, *WGIP to 'reki-shisen': 'Nihonjin no dōtoku' wo torimodosu*, Kashiwa 2019.

¹⁶ S. Sakamoto *Josei no kenri kara mita dataizai to yūsei hogo hō*, pp. 40-42; J. Morgan, *The Individual in (as) the Body Politic: Seichō no Ie and Anti-Abortion Kokutai Spiritualism in 1960s Japan*, in R. D. Eldridge and J. Morgan (eds.), *Japan in the 1960s: Ten Years of Turning Points*, Oxon 2024.

¹⁷ A. Takeuchi-Demirci, *Contraceptive Diplomacy*, p. 121.

¹⁸ *Ibid.*

unfit to breed.¹⁹ Women and teenage girls were sterilized for reasons such as being «mentally feeble» (*seishin hakujaku*), often with the consent, not of the patient, but of other members of her family.²⁰ In many areas, the scope of «consent» was limited by a poor understanding of the details of the Eugenic Protection Law²¹. These and other transgressions would come to light later, particularly in the July, 2024 Supreme Court rulings, which found, in part, that such clauses in the Eugenic Protection Law that allowed for these practices «caused, on entirely one-sided eugenic grounds, grievous sacrifices to be extracted from individuals»²². The July, 2024 court also found that «the very act of seeking the consent [of individuals] to perform sterilization surgeries in pursuit of [the clauses in question] itself constitutes an unacceptable violation of the spirit of respect for the human person and for individual dignity,» so much so that the surgeries performed under such «consent» should be considered to have been coerced²³. The 2024 rulings thus disrupted postwar eugenics, as individuals had been disrupting the same throughout the postwar period, by foregrounding those individuals in the eyes of the law, and, thereby, also in the life of society.

3. Second Disruption: The Law

The July, 2024 ruling by the Japanese Supreme Court that sterilization operations performed under the Eugenic Protection Law focused on violations of Article 13 and Article 14, Clause 1 of the Japanese Constitution. Article 13 reads, in full:

¹⁹ A 1953 publication by the Ministry of Health and Welfare stated that «eugenics operations requiring review may be performed even over the objections of the patient». Y. Takayama and Y. Hamano, *Josei shōgaisha no genjō to kongo: Yūsei hogo hō kara Botai hogo hō e no ikō no naka de*, «Yokohama Kokuritsu Daigaku Kyōiku Kiyō», 37, 1997, p. 127. See also K. Sueda, *Aichiken ni okeru Yūsei hogo hō ka de no kyōsei funin shujutsu no unyō jittai: 1966 nendo kara – 1971 nendo wo chūshin ni*, «Aichi Shukutoku Daigaku Ronshū: Fukushi Kōken Gakubu Hen», 13, 2023; H. Nakaso, *Kyū Yūsei hogo hō to kenpō 13 jō*, «Ehime Daigaku Kyōiku Gakubu Kiyō», 66, 2019, pp. 113-116; K. Hoshino and K. Matsuura, *Yūsei hogo hō Fukuoka soshō no tokuchō to genjō ni tsuite*, «Kyūshū Hōgakkai Kaihō», 2021, p. 29; T. Usui, *Kiroku wo nokoshi, kōkai suru koto no imi: kyū Yūsei hogo hō, Hansenbyō no kiroku wo daizai ni kangaeru*, «Ākaibuzugaku Kenkyū», 31, 2019, p. 34; Y. Koya, M. Muramatsu, S. Agata, and T. Furuya, *Wagakuni ni okeru jinkō ninshin chūzetsu no kōshū eisei narabini jinkōgakuteki kenkyū: sōron*, «Nihon Jinkōgakkai Kiyō», 2, 1954, pp. 1-9; and A. Kojima, M. Katō, and T. Takano, *Nagano ken ni okeru Yūsei hogo hō ni yoru jinkō ninshin chūzetsu no sui ni tsuite*, «Minzoku Eisei», 18, 1952, pp. 131-135.

²⁰ Also pertinent in many of these cases were sections twenty and twenty-one of the Mental Hygiene Law (*Seishin eisei hō*), Legislation No. 123, 1949. See S. Saibansho, «Kokka baishō seikyū jiken, nos. (o) 1341 and 1682, July 3», 2024, p. 3. See also J. Komori, *Gifu ken ni okeru shōgai no aru hito ni taisuru kyōsei funin shujutsu nikansuru ichikōsatsu: Gifu ken Yūsei hogo shinsa kaigi jiroku kara miete kuru koto*, «Gifu Kyōritsu Daigaku Ronshū», 54, 2, 2020, pp. 4-13.

²¹ U. Yamashita, *Fukuoka kennai yon chiku ni okeru kazoku keikaku no jittai chōsa (dai nana hō): jinkō ninshin chūzetsu no jitsujō*, «Kaseigaku Zasshi», 21, 1, 1970, pp. 75-82.

²² S. Saibansho, «Kokka baishō seikyū jiken, no. 1319, July 3», p. 10.

²³ *Ibid.*

All of the people shall be respected as individuals. Their right to life, liberty, and the pursuit of happiness shall, to the extent that it does not interfere with the public welfare, be the supreme consideration in legislation and in other governmental affairs.²⁴

Article 14, Clause 1, reads:

All of the people are equal under the law and there shall be no discrimination in political, economic or social relations because of race, creed, sex, social status or family origin.

In July, 2024, the Japanese Supreme Court found that the sterilization procedures were unconstitutional on the above grounds²⁵. As such, the July, 2024 rulings were indicative of a quiet revolution in Japanese jurisprudence.

Indeed, much had changed in the court's thinking about eugenics, even compared with another landmark eugenics case just five years before. On May 28, 2019, the Sendai District Court ruled in favor of two plaintiffs who had undergone forced sterilization surgery. Like the Japanese Supreme Court in 2024, the 2019 Sendai court also found that forced surgeries were in violation of Article 13 of the Japanese constitution, and that the sections in the Eugenic Protection Law which made such surgeries possible was itself therefore unconstitutional²⁶. However, while the Sendai court recognized that the former Eugenic Protection Law had brought about «grave damage» (*higai no jūdaisei*) to the plaintiffs in the case, the court failed to grant that that damage was «continuous» (*keizokusei*) or «currently present» (*genzaisei*), thereby undermining the plaintiffs' claims for damages²⁷. Furthermore, as the statute of limitations (twenty years since the time the surgery in question was performed) had expired, the court ruled that the plaintiffs could not seek compensation from the government for damages.²⁸

²⁴Translations here of the Japanese Constitution can be found at the Prime Minister of Japan's government website: https://japan.kantei.go.jp/constitution_and_government_of_japan/constitution_e.html. On Article 13, see Llompart, J. and E. Akiba, *Ningen no songen to seimei rinri, seimei hō*, Tokyo 2006, pp. 41-48.

²⁵S. Saibansho, «Kokka baishō seikyū jiken», pp. 11-12; S. Saibansho, «Kokka baishō seikyū jiken», p. 8.

²⁶H. Suzuki, *Kyū Yūsei hogo hō ni motozuku kyōsei funin shujutsu to kokusai jinken*, «Kokusai Josei», 34, 1, 2020, p. 139; see also H. Nakaso, *Kyū Yūsei hogo hō to kenpō 13 jō*, pp. 113-122.

²⁷K. Hoshino and K. Matsuura, *Yūsei hogo hō Fukuoka soshō no tokuchō to genjō ni tsuite*, «Kyūshū Hōgakkai Kaihō», 2021, p. 28.

²⁸Other courts also rejected plaintiffs' claims on similar grounds in eugenics cases following the Sendai case of 2019. See T. Watanabe, *Kyū Yūsei hogo hō soshō ni okeru kaisei mae minpō 724 jō kōdan no kōka no seigen*, «Seikei Hōgaku», 94, 2021, pp. 77, 89-94; Y. Ashino, Y. Ohashi, and A. Tsuge, *Yūsei hogo hō kara Botai hogo hō e no 'kaisei' ni okeru ripurodakutibu herusu, raitsu wo meguru kōbō: Dōmoto Akiko moto sangiingiin ni kiku*, «Meiji Gakuin Daigaku Shakaigaku Shakai Fukushigaku Kenkyū», 161, 2023, pp. 291-320; T. Yamada, *Kyū Yūsei hogo hō kokubai soshō ni okeru songai oyobi jikō, joseki kikan no kentō*, «Hō to Seiji», 71, 1, 2020, pp. 367-454; T. Ishimatsu, *Kyū Yūsei hogo hō kokka baishō seikyū soshō ni okeru joseki kikan mondai*, «Fukuoka Daigaku Hōgaku Ronsō», 67, 2023, pp. 569-691; T. Ishimatsu, *Kyū Yūsei hogo hō kokka baishō seikyū soshō ni okeru minpō 724 jō kōdan no nijūnen no joseki kikan no tekiyō seigen ni tsuite: Sendai kō han Reiwa gonon roku gatsu tsuitachi wo kien toshite*, «Fukuoka Daigaku Hōgaku Ronsō», 68, 3, 2023, pp. 413-540; and R. Yoshimura, *Kyū Yūsei hogo hō soshō' ni okeru minpō*

What had changed between 2019 and 2024 was the further emergence of the individual, both in the form of cases (casuistry) and in the form of the the social particular pressing back against the social collective, within the jurisprudential life of the law in Japan. Once the Sendai court acknowledged the existence and the moral weight of individual claims, albeit without admitting the full jurisprudential importance of those claims, it was only a matter of time before the complicating pressure of the individual, as both court case and human person, overwhelmed the parts of the legal edifice designed, as all legislation is, to keep the individual subordinate to the collective. Statute of limitations legislation could not restrain the force of casuistry in the Japanese eugenics cases. Nor could the Eugenic Protection Law itself, which fell, as unconstitutional, after the circumstances of individual victims came to the jurisprudential fore.

Other cases prior to the 2019 Sendai case help explain how this pressure built. Researcher Hirata Katsumasa notes that a January, 2018 case brought before the Sendai court seeking compensation from the Japanese government over forced sterilization operations prompted many throughout Japan to launch investigations into institutional histories for similar examples of forced sterilizations²⁹. To give just one example, on March 28, 1952, a twenty-eight-year-old man in Tottori Prefecture was castrated against his will on the advice of a doctor, who believed the castration would reduce a problem of physical violence the man had displayed toward his mother³⁰. This was hardly the only such procedure carried out in Japan at the time³¹. Likewise, Hansen's disease cases in Japan are filled with information about discrimination, forced sterilization, forced abortions, forced quarantine (even to the point of internal exile to lepers-only islands), and other sorrows. Clause three, section one, number three of the 1948 Eugenic Protection Law provided for «eugenic operations,» that is, sterilizations and abortions, to be performed on Hansen's disease patients and those thought to be genetically susceptible to the disease³². The Rai yobō hō (Leprosy Prevention Law) of 1953 further stipulated that those suffering from Hansen's disease could be placed into lepers' sanatoria, along with the patients'

724 jō kōdan (*kyū kitei*) no tekiyō seigen nikansuru saikin no kakyūshin hanketsu wo dō miruka, «Ritsumeikan Hōgaku», 411-412, 2023, pp. 520-547. However, on April 24, 2019, the Japanese Diet passed a law authorizing a one-time payment to those who had undergone «eugenic surgeries» under the old Eugenic Protection Law. See S. Takara, *Kyū Yūsei hogo hō Sendai chisai hanketsu no kentō*, «Okinawa Daigaku Jinbun Gakubu Kiyō», 24, 2021, p. 101. See also K. Hoshino and K. Matsuura, *Yūsei hogo hō Fukuoka soshō no tokuchō to genjō ni tsuite*, pp. 28, 31-32; S. Takara, *Kyū Yūsei hogo hō Sendai chisai hanketsu no kentō*, pp. 103, 105-107; and M. Aoi, *Ronsetsu*, pp. 32-37.

²⁹ K. Hirata, *Yūsei hogo hō to shōgaisha no jinken: 1950nendai no danshu (kyosei) jiken no kentō*, «Nagasaki Daigaku Kyōiku Gakubu Kyōiku Jissen Kenkyū Kiyō», 18, 2019, p. 147.

³⁰ K. Hirata, *Yūsei hogo hō to shōgaisha no jinken*, pp. 147-148.

³¹ K. Hirata, *Yūsei hogo hō to shōgaisha no jinken*, p. 151.

³² S. Saibansho Jimu Sōkyoku, «Hansenbyō wo riyū tosuru kaitei basho shitei nikansuru chōsa hōkokusho», 2016, p. 36.

spouse and guardians.³³ Individual efforts, such as political action and petitions, led eventually to the abolition of the Rai yobō hō in 1995³⁴. The individual had again overcome the anonymizing, eugenic collective. There is poetic justice, then, perhaps, in that the Minister of Health, Labour and Welfare issued an official apology on March 23, 2002, addressed directly to former and current Hansen's disease patients³⁵. The government, represented by an individual, spoke to individuals which the government had harmed by law and in the name of eugenic collectivism, thus achieving, if only fleetingly, the equality, individual to individual, to which the same government professes to aspire³⁶.

Japan's laws were also challenged, in a casuistic, individual-centered way, by the human disaster which unfolded in the wake of the Empire of Japan's defeat in the Greater East Asia War. With the booming political and civilizational refrains of the old order silenced, the individual emerged again from the collective to confront the legal structures that had enabled his and her subordination to the whole. As Japanese settlers fled Manchuria, the Korean Peninsula, and elsewhere following Japan's surrender to the Allied Forces, countless Japanese women were raped by enemy soldiers and local men. Anthropologist Izumi Seiichi (1915-1970) helped at a facility in Futsukaichi, near Fukuoka, to care for these women and their children, many of the latter of whom were conceived in rape³⁷. The dreams of empire, shattered, brought before the eyes of authorities in Japan the individuals of whom the empire had been constructed, and who suffered grievously as the empire was destroyed.

Abortion presented a formidable challenge to the law in another way. On April 17 and 18, 1973, a physician named Kikuta Noboru placed ads in his local papers in Ishinomaki, Sendai, seeking adoptive parents for a newborn boy. This simple act precipitated a national crisis over adoption law³⁸. The reason for this was that Japanese law required adoptive parents to indicate the fact

³³ There have been two laws in Japan known as Rai yobō hō. In the first, passed in 1907, the name for «leprosy» (*rai*) was written with a Chinese character (癩); in the second, passed in 1953, the same word was written with the Japanese syllabary (らい). See J. Ikai, *Rai yobō hō kaisei iinkai no mondō (ni): Raiyobōkyōkai ni tsuite shitsumon zokushutsu*, «Ikai Jihō», 1907, 1931, pp. 16-18; and M. Makino, *Hansenbyō no rekishi ni manabu: Hansenbyō ryōyōjo iryō hyakunen wo furikaeru*, «Nihon Hansenbyō Gakkai Zasshi», 79, 1, 2010, pp. 25-36. See also S. Saibansho Jimu Sōkyoku, «Hansenbyō wo riyū tosuru kaitei basho shitei nikansuru chōsa hōkokusho», p. 36; and S. L. Burns, *Kingdom of the Sick*, pp. 2, 132-166.

³⁴ S. Saibansho Jimu Sōkyoku, «Hansenbyō wo riyū tosuru kaitei basho shitei nikansuru chōsa hōkokusho», pp. 38-39.

³⁵ S. Saibansho Jimu Sōkyoku, «Hansenbyō wo riyū tosuru kaitei basho shitei nikansuru chōsa hōkokusho», p. 41.

³⁶ See, e.g., S. Saibansho Jimu Sōkyoku, «Yūshikisha iinkai iken». «Hansenbyō wo riyū tosuru kaitei basho shitei nikansuru chōsa hōkokusho (besshi)», pp. 4-5.

³⁷ M. Shimokawa, *Bōkyaku no hikiageshi: Izumi Seiichi to Futsukaichi hoyōjo*, Fukuoka 2017, pp. 285-289; see also Y. Matsubara, *Hikiagesha iryō kyūgo ni okeru soshikiteki jinkō ninshin chūzetsu: Yūsei hogo hō zenshi*, in H. Tsuboi H. (ed.), *Jendā to seiseiji: sengo Nihon wo yomikaeru*, Kyoto, 2019.

³⁸ J. Morgan, *Kikuta Noboru and Adoption Law in Japan*, «Reitaku Daigaku Kiyō», 102, 2019, pp. 35-44; K. Yoshida, *Kikuta ishi jiken to Yūsei hogo hō kaisei mondai: 'umu jiyū' wo megutte*, «Igaku Tetsugaku, Igaku Rinri», 29, 2011, pp. 55-56.

of a child's adoption on the family registry (*koseki*), which left a permanent record of different parentage which many couples, for obvious reasons, wanted to avoid. Dr. Kikuta had been skirting the law by placing unwanted children with adoptive parents without leaving official records of the act. This allowed otherwise reluctant prospective adoptive parents to adopt children with peace of mind, knowing that the adopted child would not have to face the trauma of later learning that his or her parents were not biological relatives. This worked as a stopgap measure, but it remained just that, a temporary fix. Dr. Kikuta wanted to change the law in Japan to save the many children who were being aborted because of a lack of adoptive parents. Dr. Kikuta's advocacy placed society's focus squarely on individual cases, on the child as he or she existed prior to being recognized in the framework of the law via the *koseki*. It was a work of public casuistry in that Dr. Kikuta used his own discernment, in the light of moral principles (Dr. Kikuta had been a Buddhist but had converted to Christianity), to privilege the individual over the utilitarian logic of postwar eugenics. Amendments to the Civil Code of Japan were considered in the wake of Dr. Kikuta's challenge to the logic and moral scope of the law.

A similar mood of national soul-searching prompted by the casuistry of the individual versus the eugenic nation-state occurred four years after Dr. Kikuta's fateful advertisements. In 1977, mass screening of newborns for certain genetic diseases was introduced under the auspices of the Eugenic Protection Law. The same law ensured that those whose children might be born with genetic diseases or even «genetic mental feebleness» (*idensei seishin hakujaku*) could seek therapeutic abortions³⁹.

4. Third Disruption: Contingency

The painful history of eugenics in Japan is, at the same time, an opportunity to reflect on differences in Japanese and Western modes of dealing with contingency. In general, post-Enlightenment Western philosophers have tended to emphasize a generalization of contingency in ethical questions and to downplay individual discernment, a tendency perhaps best reflected in Immanuel Kant's (1724-1804) categorical imperative⁴⁰. In Japan, by contrast, moral decisions tend to be made in context, that is, casuistically. The history of postwar eugenics

³⁹ E. Sasatani, *Shinseiji masu sukuriningu dōnyū go no hoinsha kensaku to shusshō mae shindan*, «Ritsumeikan Ningenkagaku Kenkyū», 37, 2018, pp. 19-20; see also K. Yokozuka, *Hahayo! Korosuna*, Tokyo 2007, pp. 128-138; Y. Matsubara, *Nihon: sengo no Yūsei hogo hō toiu na no danshu hō*, pp. 214-219; and S. Inoue S, *Taiji towa nanika: sono hōteki kōsatsu*, in Nihon Kyōbunsha (ed.), *Taiji wa ningen denai noka: Yūsei hogo hō no gimonten*. Tokyo 1982.

⁴⁰ Kant did admit of some casuistry, but in a most peculiar, very much generalized way. See, e.g., H. D. Kittsteiner, *Kant and Casuistry*, in Edmund Leites (ed.), *Conscience and Casuistry in Early Modern Europe*, Cambridge 1988. See also J. von Platz, *Singularity without Equivalence: The Complex Unity of Kant's Categorical Imperative*, «Journal of Value Inquiry», 50, 2016, p. 372; L. Denis, *Abortion and Kant's Formula of Universal Law*, «Canadian Journal of Philosophy», 37, 4, 2007, pp. 547-580; S. B. Kim, *The Formation of Kant's Casuistry and Method Problems of Applied Ethics*, «Kant Studien», 100, 3, 2009, pp. 332-345; and M. Ananth, *Clini-*

is an opportunity, therefore, albeit one gained at incalculable human cost, to rediscover an alternative to Kantian ethics, including the personalism espoused by Emmanuel Levinas (1906-1995), and the casuistic philosophy of Stephen Toulmin (1922-2009) and Thomas Fleming in relation to life-ethics questions such as abortion and palliative care⁴¹. The 2024 case, while declaring swaths of the postwar eugenic legal regime unconstitutional, also indirectly hearkens back to a much earlier time when communal living was the norm of Japanese society. *Mabiki*, *ko-oroshi*, *kogaeshi* and other euphemisms for abortion long predated the introduction of birth control ideology and techniques from the West, and abortion before the influx of eugenic ideology in Japan was always an individualized decision, without attempts to justify the practice or to deny the humanity of the unborn⁴². There is also inherent in eugenics the Darwinian tension (and here we must remember that Darwinism – including its cousin, Social Darwinism – is a western ideology) between the imperfect individual and the species ever in the process of evolving⁴³. In postwar Japan much of eugenics debate, especially regarding questions of abortion, has tended to be framed in terms of individual autonomy⁴⁴. And yet, before eugenics came to dominate life and ethics questions in the postwar, such questions were most often decided on individualized, that is to say, on casuistic terms.

The concept of individual autonomy also stands in contradiction to the practice of forced sterilization, one of the hallmarks of postwar eugenics in Japan. As researcher Toshimitsu Keiko notes, while the Eugenic Protection Law «ostensibly» (*hyōmenjō wa*) stipulated that sterilization operations were to be carried out «with the consent of the patient» (*honnin no dōi ni motozuku*), in

cal Decision-Making: The Case against the New Casuistry, «Issues in Law and Medicine», 32, 2, 2017, p. 146.

⁴¹ A. R. Jonsen, and S. Toulmin, *The Abuse of Casuistry: A History of Moral Reasoning*, Berkeley, 1988; T. Fleming, *The Morality of Everyday Life: Rediscovering an Ancient Alternative to the Liberal Tradition*, Columbia, 2004; S. Tsuru, *Mō hitotsu no jinkaku gainen: Revinasu no shisō wo tegakari ni*, «Hattatsuningengaku Ronsō», 10, 2007, pp. 69-75; J. Krueger, *The Space between Us: Embodiment and Intersubjectivity in Watsuji and Levinas*, in L. Kalmanson, F. Garrett, and S. Mattice (eds.), *Levinas and Asian Thought*. Pittsburgh 2013.

⁴² Y. Kakimoto. *Chūzetsu no jiyū wa sentakuteki chūzetsu wo fukumu no ka? Yūseishugi to jendā*, in «Kyōto Joshi Daigaku Gendai Shakai Kenkyū», 9, 2006, p. 80; Y. Fujime, *Sei no rekishigaku*, pp. 120-123; L. Wardle, 'Crying Stones: A Comparison of Abortion in Japan and the United States', «New York Law School Journal of International and Comparative Law», 14, 2, 1993, pp. 187-192; and F. Drixler, *Mabiki: Infanticide and Population Growth in Eastern Japan, 1660-1950*. Berkeley, 2013.

⁴³ K. Ōkura, *Jinruiidengaku kara mita Yūsei hogo hō no tekiyō nikansuru gigi*, «Nihon Senten Ijō Gakkai Kaihō», 14, 3, 1974, pp. 178-179; see also M. Nagura, *Seimeikagaku toshite no 'shinka, iden' kyōiku no hitsuyōsei nitsuite ichikōsatsu: sengo chūtō rika kyōiku no hensen oyobi shinkaron, yūseigaku nikansuru jidai shichō yori*, «Nihon Kagaku Kyōiku Gakkai Dai 45 Nenka Ronbunshū», 2021, pp. 417-420; and T. Kitagaki, *Shakai Dainizumu towa nandatta noka: jūkyū seiki kōhan ni okeru Furansu no jirei*, in Yamazaki Kiyoko (ed.), *Seimei no rinri 2: yūseigaku no jidai wo koete*, Fukuoka 2008.

⁴⁴ T. Aono, *Jiko kettei no shisō to yūsei hogo hō no kaishaku: hōteki kenri toshite no jinkō ninshin chūzetsu no jiyū*, «Daigaku Kyōiku Kaihō Sentā Kiyō», 15, 1995, pp. 37-52; M. Morioka, *Nihon ni okeru feminizumu seimei rinri no keisei katei: 70-80 nendai Yūsei hogo hō kaiaku hantai undō ga teiki suru mono*, «Seimei Rinri», 5, 1, 1995, p. 62.

practice this was not always the case⁴⁵. Clause three of the law, for example, which as noted above allows physicians to override consent practices in the event of mental illness, «mental feebleness» (*seishin hakujaku*), manic depression (*sōutsubyō*), or underage status, seriously compromises the principle of individual autonomy. So does the same clause's stipulation that the consent of the woman's husband be obtained before performing abortions on eugenics grounds even if the woman herself is a mentally capable adult⁴⁶.

Compounding the contradiction between claims to respect individual autonomy and practices that undercut it is that, according to researcher Yui Hideki, there is a dearth of public records on individual procedures carried out under clause three of the Eugenic Protection Law (although there are such records for procedures carried out under clauses four and twelve)⁴⁷. Yui cites Matsubara Yōko's conclusion that even when individual choice, in the form of decisions made by married couples, was taken into consideration in questions of abortion, in reality physicians applied pressure to couples in reproductive matters on the basis of societal benefits, or what I would gloss as utilitarian concerns⁴⁸. The individual, always the bearer of contingency whether in law (casuistry) or in life, was relegated by the postwar eugenics regime to a distant second-class standing, even as individual autonomy was elevated to a political mainstay within that same regime.

The «Movement to Avoid Giving Birth to Unhappy Children» (*Fukō na kodomo wo umarenai undō*) from 1966, under which discrimination against disabled people whom the state deemed unfit to have children, also exemplified the collectivist eugenic trend of the age⁴⁹. To put it differently, the American-dominated Japanese postwar can be understood as a period of fanatical anti-casuistry, in which the complication of norms by individuals was viewed unfavorably by the Japanese government and by others, such as the American Occupation forces, interested in maintaining the government and the status quo it represented and perpetuated. Abortions under this dispensation increased dramatically, from some 100,000 in 1949 to some 1.17 million in 1955 – although the numbers may be much higher, as many abortions may have been performed without notification by the abortionist to the authorities⁵⁰. The drive to avoid having «unhappy children» seems, in retrospect, to have been a drive to avoid any challenges to complete elite control over social contingency.⁵¹

⁴⁵ K. Toshimitsu, *Yūsei hogo hō no moto de no kyōsei funin shujutsu to kōbunsho*, p. 129.

⁴⁶ H. Yui, *1950 nendai kara 60 nendai Nihon ni okeru kazoku keikaku to yūsei shujutsu: Yūsei hogo hō 3 jō ni motozuku yūsei shujutsu*, «Ritsumeikan Ningenkagaku Kenkyū», 48, 2024, pp. 33-34; see also M. Oseki, *Yūsei hogo hō to seishinbyō*, «Sanfujinka no Shinpo», 2, 1, 1950, p. 2.

⁴⁷ H. Yui, *1950 nendai kara 60 nendai Nihon ni okeru kazoku keikaku to yūsei shujutsu*, p. 35.

⁴⁸ H. Yui, *1950 nendai kara 60 nendai Nihon ni okeru kazoku keikaku to yūsei shujutsu*, p. 42.

⁴⁹ T. Furui and M. Furui, *Nijū seiki de owaranakatta yūsei shisō*, pp. 30-31; see also S. Sakamoto, *Josei no kenri kara mita dataizai to yūsei hogo hō*, p. 36; and Matsubara Y. 2000. *Nihon: sengo no Yūsei hogo hō toiu na no danshu hō*, pp. 208-211.

⁵⁰ S. Sakamoto, *Josei no kenri kara mita dataizai to yūsei hogo hō*, p. 37.

⁵¹ On elite control of society in postwar Japan, see L. Hein, *Powerful Men, Reasonable Words: Political Culture and Expertise in Twentieth-Century Japan*, Berkeley, 2005.

It is particularly fitting that women in Japan were at the forefront of eugenics debates, as childbirth, by which a new, paradigm-defying individual comes into the world, is a kind of casuistry in action, an irruption of contingency within a pre-existing pattern. Women's history scholar Andrea Germer writes that Hiratsuka Raichō (1886-1971) and Yamada Waka (1879-1957) followed «Swedish social reformer Ellen Key [(1849-1926)]» in advocating for the role of the state in protecting «pregnant women and mothers,» over and against poet Yosano Akiko (1878-1942), who took an individualist position⁵². Yamakawa Kikue (1890-1980), by contrast to Hiratsuka, Yosano, and Yamada, followed August Bebel (1840-1913) and «German socialist women» in «denounc[ing] bourgeois feminism and maintain[ing] that the emancipation of women could not be achieved without radically transforming the class system»⁵³. «Feminist anarchist» Takamura Itsue (1894-1964), for her part, engaged in «a thorough critique of Western philosophy and its misogynist aspects [...] alongside a critique of Western feminisms, modernity, the city, and capitalism,» despite being «influenced [...] by Western theories such as that of American sociologist Lester Frank Ward [(1841-1913)] who asserted the biological hierarchy of the female as the primary sex in a chapter of his *Pure Sociology* (1914)»⁵⁴. And «statist feminists» such as Ichikawa Fusae (1893-1981), while criticizing the all-male makeup of the League of Nations, «actively cooperate[d] with the [Japanese] government after Japan had left» the League⁵⁵. As eugenics ideology came into Japan, some feminists advocated for autonomy and control over reproduction, while others emphasized the priority of the collective (society, the nation, even the Japanese ethnic group) over the individual. And yet, in a casuistic sense, women, as the bearers of embodied contingency, were those whose experiences would, much later, re-enter the eyes of the law and the life of the collective. This happened when their sufferings, bodily and mentally, in the name of eugenics came gradually to the surface in court cases brought before panels of judges at district courts throughout Japan as well as the Supreme Court in Tokyo.

Reading the history of eugenics in postwar Japan, it becomes easy to understand why, in a 1964 essay, researcher Ogawa Setsu notes that, while no law is able to avoid subsequent contradictions, the benefits which the Eugenics Protection Act brought to Japan cannot be said to have outweighed the costs⁵⁶. For example, Ogawa notes, abortions were carried out with, at best, skirting compliance with the law, which led in many cases, Ogawa argues, to outright rejection of the law in practice⁵⁷. Not only this, but the damage which wanton abortion caused to women's physical and mental health, as well as to the damage

⁵² A. Germer, *Japanese Feminists after Versailles: Between the State and the Ethnic Nation*, «Journal of Women's History», 25, 3, 2013, 95-96.

⁵³ *Ibid.*, p. 96.

⁵⁴ A. Germer, *Japanese Feminists after Versailles*, pp. 102, 105.

⁵⁵ *Ibid.*, p. 104.

⁵⁶ S. Ogawa, *Yūsei hōgo hō no mondaiten ni tsuite*, pp. 17-18.

⁵⁷ *Ibid.*, p. 18.

to sexual morals which it wrought, was, Ogawa found, «lamentable» (*ureu beki*)⁵⁸. Similar effects of the Eugenic Protection Law on individual people can be seen in the novels of Kawasaki Chōtarō (1901-1985), who wrote about the effects of the Eugenic Protection Law on individual prostitutes⁵⁹. In the pursuit of the generality and collectivism of eugenics, the individual was being asked to suffer greatly, although this suffering was by and large, in turn, factored back into the greater good to be gained from eugenics practices (a greater good which Ogawa largely exposed as non-existent).

This disappearance of the individual within the general, of the case within the law, is a feature of the modern world, and not just of postwar Japan under the influence of Western eugenics ideology. There are always before us two choices, in the law and in life more broadly: to see the individual qua an individual and to use our moral sense to discern our response to him or her, or to defer to some principle, whatever it may be, and dismiss some or all of the individual's particularity in favor of the much easier method of proceeding along a pre-determined path. In the 1950s, Danish advocate for disability-related policy reform Niels Erik Bank-Mikkelsen (1919-1990) began calling for those with disabilities to live «normal» lives, which led to a normalization movement for the disabled with Japan as well⁶⁰. Those with disabilities who had been sent to live in «colonies» (*koronī*) during the prewar, wartime, and postwar period were moved into facilities such as group homes more conducive to living lives as like as possible to the surrounding populations⁶¹.

This Western-influenced attempt at «normalization» should be contrasted with earlier, prewar Japanese experiments in independence for those differently abled. In the early 1920s, for instance, a reformer named Ishii Ryōichi (1867-1937) founded Takinogawa Gakuen, the first facility in Japan dedicated to the care of the mentally disabled⁶². Ishii's stated goal was to enable patients to live independent lives while avoiding the insults and abuses such people often suffered in society, as well as the ills of drink and prostitution which often plagued them. It is true that Ishii wanted to ensure that the mentally handicapped did not become burdens to their families and to the state as a whole⁶³. But Ishii's work overall mirrored much of the much older history in Japan of seeking maximum independence for sufferers from Hansen's disease, allowing the individual to make his or her own choices in tandem with, but not subservient to, the needs

⁵⁸ S. Ogawa, *Yūsei hogo hō no mondaiten ni tsuite*, p. 18.

⁵⁹ Y. Yamamoto, *Baishun bōshi hō to bungaku: Kawasaki Chōtarō no baai*, «Shōhoku Kiyō», 29, 2008, pp. 109-120.

⁶⁰ M. Kobayashi, *Shōgaisha no koronī shūyō to shijōka ato no chiiki seikatsu ni tsūtei suru mono*, «Shakaifukushi Gakubu Ronshū», 17, 2021, p. 111; see also S: Sowa, *Nōmaraijeshon to shakai-teki, kyōikuteki inkurūjon*. Kyoto 2010.

⁶¹ M. Kobayashi, *Shōgaisha no koronī shūyō to shijōka ato no chiiki seikatsu ni tsūtei suru mono*, pp. 110-112; see also H. Yōda, *Shōgaisha sabetsu no shakaigaku*, Tokyo 1999, pp. 217-228.

⁶² M. Kobayashi, Y. *Shōgaisha no koronī shūyō to shijōka ato no chiiki seikatsu ni tsūtei suru mono*, p. 119; see also Tsumagari, *Ishii Ryōichi*, Tokyo 2021.

⁶³ M. Kobayashi, *Shōgaisha no koronī shūyō to shijōka ato no chiiki seikatsu ni tsūtei suru mono*, p. 119

of society. With the charitable work of Ishii and other likeminded reformers in prewar Japan, we are a far, far cry from the heinous July 26, 2016 incident in Sagamihara, Kanagawa Prefecture, in which an employee named Uematsu Satoshi murdered nineteen people and wounded twenty-six others at a group home for the mentally disabled⁶⁴. Uemura later claimed to have been inspired by the master eugenicist himself, Adolf Hitler (1889-1945)⁶⁵.

5. Conclusion

There were calls throughout the postwar in Japan to abolish the 1948 Eugenics Protection Law, but those were unheeded or unsuccessful until 1996, when the law, as amended several times since its original passage, was finally repealed in part⁶⁶. Calls for revision were varied, and reflected tremendous changes and currents in Japanese society, such as the rise of feminism⁶⁷. But the failure to abolish the law until nearly the end of the twentieth century may speak of much deeper currents in Japanese life and law during that time. For example, the stasis of the constitutional order in Japan, where the current constitution remains exactly as the Americans wrote it and the Japanese passed it into law in 1946, could be a symptom, or a cause, or both, of the war against contingency in postwar Japan.

That casuistry has only recently emerged, and even more recently, in July of 2024, triumphed, over the postwar eugenics paradigm, is bound up with a whole array of other things in the postwar, a whole way of shunting the individual to the side while privileging the needs of powers that be. In 1996 the name of the Eugenic Protection Law, as partially repealed and revised, was changed to the Maternal Protection Law (*Botai hogo hō*), although the updated legislative provisions, including the long overdue deletion of language allowing for forced sterilizations on eugenics grounds, did nothing to protect maternal bodies (*botai*) from abortions deemed necessary for economic or psychological reasons⁶⁸. The war against contingency continues, then, but so does the fight for the individual – in court cases, and in shared life – in postwar Japan.

⁶⁴ T. Yokoyama, *Nihon no yūseigakushi kenkyū no korekara wo kangaeru tameni: Sagamihara jiken to Yūsei hogo hō hōdō e no shoken*, «Kagakushi Kenkyū», 60, 2021, pp. 66-77.

⁶⁵ S. Shimbun, «Sagamihara shi 19 nin shisatsu jiken wa Nachisu no T4 sakusen datta noka? Yogisha ga kanka sareta Hitorā no yuganda shisō ga himotoku», August 8, 2016.

⁶⁶ J. Morgan, *The Individual in (as) the Body Politic*; M. Morioka, *Yūsei hogo hō kaisei wo meguru seimei rinri*, pp. 213-218; and S. Inoue, *Yūsei hogo hō kaisei wo meguru mondai to iken*, Tokyo 1968-1969.

⁶⁷ K. Namase, *1970 nendai shoki ni okeru 'Yūsei hogo hō kaiaku soshi' wo meguru ūman ribu undō to shōgaisha mondai nikansuru oboegaki*, «Momoyama Gakuin Daigaku Kirisutokyō Ronshū», 33, 1997, pp. 245-260.

⁶⁸ S. Sakamoto, *Josei no kenri kara mita dataizai to yūsei hogo hō*, pp. 43-44; see also I. Konuma, *Yūsei shisō to jinken*, pp. 170-171; Y. Matsubara, *Nihon: sengo no Yūsei hogo hō toiu na no danshu hō*, pp. 229-231, 234-236; and K. Tsukahara, *Chūzetsu gijutsu to ripurodakutivu raitsu: feminisuto rinri no shiten kara*, Tokyo 2014, pp. 120-121.

References

- Akiba, E. 2010. *'Hito' no hajimari wo meguru shinri no kōsatsu*. Tokyo.
- Ananth, M. 2017. *Clinical Decision-Making: The Case against the New Casuistry*, in «Issues in Law and Medicine», vol. 32, no. 2, pp. 143-171.
- Aoi M. 2019. *Ronsetsu: kyū Yūsei hogo hō no ikensei oyobi sono moto de yūsei shujutsu wo uketa higaisha e no kyūsai rippō fusonzai no ikensei narabini kokka baishō hō jō no ihōsei ni tsuite*, in «Gakushūin Hōmu Kenkyū», vol. 13, pp. 1-38.
- Aoki Y. 2004. *Hansenbyō ryōyōjo nyūshosha noshintai shōgai: Setouchi san en nyūshosha no jittai chōsa niyoru kenkyū*, in «Nihon Kōshū Eisei Zasshi», vol. 51, no. 9, pp. 741-752.
- Aono T. 1995. *Jiko kettei no shisō to yūsei hogo hō no kaishaku: hōteki kenri toshite no jinkō ninshin chūzetsu no jiyū*, in «Daigaku Kyōiku Kaihō Sentā Kiyō», no. 15, pp. 37-52.
- Ashino Y., Ōhashi Y., and Tsuge A. 2023. *Yūsei hogo hō kara Botai hogo hō e no 'kaisei' ni okeru ripurodakutibu herusu, raitsu wo meguru kōbō: Dōmoto Akiko moto sangiingiin ni kiku*, in «Meiji Gakuin Daigaku Shakaigaku Shakai Fukushigaku Kenkyū», vol. 161, pp. 291-320.
- Beck, E. M. 2015. *Judge Lynch Denied: Combating Mob Violence in the American South, 1877-1950*, in «Southern Cultures», vol. 21, no. 2, pp. 117-139.
- Black, E. 2003. *War against the Weak: Eugenics and America's Campaign to Create a Master Race*. Washington, DC.
- Boeckmann, C. 2000. *A Question of Character: Scientific Racism and the Genres of American Fiction, 1892-1912*. Tuscaloosa, AL.
- Burns, S. L. 2019. *Kingdom of the Sick: A History of Leprosy and Japan*. Honolulu, HI.
- Castles, K. 2005. *Review of Unnatural Selections: Eugenics in American Modernism and the Harlem Renaissance, by Daylanne K. English*, in «Journal of Southern History», vol. 71, no. 3, pp. 727-728.
- Chazono, T. 2014. *Panpan towa dare nanoka: kyacchi toiu senryōki no seibōryoku to GI tonno shinmitsusei*. Tokyo.
- Chinitz, D. 2006. *The New Harlem Renaissance Studies*, in «Modernism/Modernity», vol. 13, no. 2, pp. 375-382.
- Denis, L. 2007. *Abortion and Kant's Formula of Universal Law*, in «Canadian Journal of Philosophy», vol. 37, no. 4, pp. 547-580.
- Doak, K. 2019. *Tanaka Kōtarō and World Law: Rethinking the Natural Law Order outside the West*. Cham, Switzerland.
- Drixler, F. 2013. *Mabiki: Infanticide and Population Growth in Eastern Japan, 1660-1950*. Berkeley, CA.
- Ehalt, da Silva R.. 2022. *Theology in the Dark: The Missionary Casuistry of Japan Jesuits and Dominicans during the Tokugawa Persecution (1616-1622)*, in Manuel Bastias Saavedra, ed. *Norms beyond Empire: Law-Making and Local Normativities in Iberian Asia, 1500-1800*. Leiden.
- Fleming, T. 2004. *The Morality of Everyday Life: Rediscovering an Ancient Alternative to the Liberal Tradition*. Columbia, MO.

- Fujime, Y. 1997. *Sei no rekishigaku: kōshō seido, dataizai taisei kara Baishun bōshi hō, Yūsei hogo hō taisei e*. Tokyo.
- Fujino, Y. 1998. *Nihon fashizumu to yūsei shisō*. Kyoto.
- Furui, T., Furui M. 2021. *Nijū seiki de owaranakatta yūsei shisō: shōgai to tomo ni ikiru jinsei ga hitsuzen no jidai ni*, in «Ōsaka Kawasaki Rihabiriteishon Daigaku Kiyō», vol. 15, pp. 23-34.
- Galton, F. 1883. *Inquiries into Human Faculty and Its Development*. New York.
- Galton, F. 1904. *Eugenics: Its Definition, Scope, and Aims*, in «American Journal of Sociology», vol. 10, no. 1, pp. 1-25.
- Germer, A. 2013. *Japanese Feminists after Versailles: Between the State and the Ethnic Nation*, in «Journal of Women's History», vol. 25, no. 3, pp. 92-115.
- Gershon, L. 2015. *Margaret Sanger's Eugenics Defense*, in «JSTOR Daily», December 18: <https://daily.jstor.org/margaret-sangers-eugenics-defense/>
- Ginzburg, C., Biasiori, L. (eds.), 2019. *A Historical Approach to Casuistry: Norms and Exceptions in a Comparative Perspective*. London.
- Griseri, P. 2008. *In Defence of Principles? A Response to Lurie and Albin*, in «Journal of Business Ethics», vol. 83, pp. 615-625.
- Hein, L. 2005. *Powerful Men, Reasonable Words: Political Culture and Expertise in Twentieth-Century Japan*. Berkeley, CA.
- Hirata, K. 2019. *Yūsei hogo hō to shōgaisha no jinken: 1950nendai no danshu (kyosei) jiken no kentō*, in «Nagasaki Daigaku Kyōiku Gakubu Kyōiku Jissen Kenkyū Kiyō», vol. 18, pp. 147-155.
- Hiroshima, K. 2020. *Sengo Nihon jinkō seisakushi kara kangaeru*, in «Nihon Kenkō Gakkaishi», vol. 86, no. 5, pp. 231-241.
- Hoshino, K. and Matsuura, K. 2021. *Yūsei hogo hō Fukuoka soshō no tokuchō to genjō ni tsuite*, in «Kyūshū Hōgakkai Kaihō», pp. 28-36.
- Iida, K. 2004. *Human Rights and Sexual Abuse: The Impact of International Human Rights Law on Japan*, in «Human Rights Quarterly», vol. 26, no. 2, pp. 428-453.
- Ikai J. 1931. *Rai yobō hō kaisei iinkai no mondō (ni): Raiyobōkyōkai ni tsuite shitsumon zokushutsu*, in «Ikai Jihō», no. 1907, pp. 16-18.
- Ikeda R. (S.). 1942. *Shidōsha minzoku no yūseigakuteki ishin*. Osaka.
- Inoue N. 1973. *Waga mae ni michi wa hiraku: Inoue Natsue jijoden*. Tokyo.
- Inoue S. 1968-1969. *Yūsei hogo hō kaisei wo meguru mondai to iken*. Tokyo.
- Inoue S. 1982. *Taiji towa nanika: sono hōteki kōsatsu*, in Nihon Kyōbunsha, ed. *Taiji wa ningen denai noka: Yūsei hogo hō no gimonten*. Tokyo.
- Ishimatsu T. 2023. *Kyū Yūsei hogo hō kokka baishō seikyū soshō ni okeru joseki kikan mondai*, in «Fukuoka Daigaku Hōgaku Ronsō», vol. 67, pp. 569-691.
- Ishimatsu T. 2023a. *Kyū Yūsei hogo hō kokka baishō seikyū soshō ni okeru minpō 724 jō kōdan no nijūnen no joseki kikan no tekiyō seigen ni tsuite: Sendai kō han Reiwa gonen rokugatsu tsuitachi wo kien toshite*, in «Fukuoka Daigaku Hōgaku Ronsō», vol. 68, no. 3, pp. 413-540.
- Jonsen, A. R. and S. Toulmin. 1988. *The Abuse of Casuistry: A History of Moral Reasoning*. Berkeley, CA.

- Kabe, K. 2022. *Seiiku genkai no seimei rinri*, in «Daiyonjūkai Shūsankigaku Shinpojiumu Sharokushū», pp. 18-22.
- Kakimoto, Y. 2006. *Chūzetsu no jiyū wa sentakuteki chūzetsu wo fukumu no ka? Yūseibugi to jendā*, in «Kyōto Joshi Daigaku Gendai Shakai Kenkyū», 9, pp. 79-91.
- Kim, S. B. 2009. *The Formation of Kant's Casuistry and Method Problems of Applied Ethics*, in «Kant Studien», 100, 3, pp. 332-345.
- Kitagaki, T. 2008. *Shakai Dāuinizumu towa nandatta noka: jūkyū seiki kōhan ni okeru Furansu no jirei*, in Yamazaki Kiyoko, ed. *Seimei no rinri 2: yūseigaku no jidai wo koete*. Fukuoka.
- Kittsteiner, H. D. 1988. *Kant and Casuistry*, in Edmund Leites, ed. *Conscience and Casuistry in Early Modern Europe*. Cambridge, UK.
- Kobayashi M. 2021. *Shōgaisha no koronī shūyō to shijōka ato no chiiki seikatsu ni tsūtei suru mono*, in «Shakaifukushi Gakubu Ronshū», 17, pp. 109-130.
- Kojima A., Katō M., Takano T., 1952. *Nagano ken ni okeru Yūsei hogo hō ni yoru jinkō ninshin chūzetsu no sui ni tsuite*, «Minzoku Eisei» 18, pp. 131-135.
- Komori J. 2020. *Gifu ken ni okeru shōgai no aru hito ni taisuru kyōsei funin shujutsu nikansuru ichikōsatsu: Gifu ken Yūsei hogo shinsa kaigi jiroku kara miete kuru koto*, «Gifu Kyōritsu Daigaku Ronshū», 54, 2, pp. 57-73.
- Konuma I. 2018. *Yūsei shisō to jinken: yūsei hogo hō no keizaiteki jōkō ni kansuru ichikōsatsu*, «Hikaku Nihongaku Kyōiku Kenkyū Bumon Kenkyū Nenpō», 14, pp. 168-173.
- Koya, Y., Muramatsu, M., Agata S., and Furuya, T. 1954. *Wagakuni ni okeru jinkō ninshin chūzetsu no kōshū eisei narabini jinkōgakuteki kenkyū: sōron*, in «Nihon Jinkōgakkai Kiyō», vol. 2, pp. 1-9.
- Krueger, J. 2013. *The Space between Us: Embodiment and Intersubjectivity in Watsuji and Levinas*, in L. Kalmanson, F. Garrett, and S. Mattice, eds. *Levinas and Asian Thought*. Pittsburgh, PA.
- Kühl, S. 1994. *The Nazi Connection: Eugenics, American Racism, and German National Socialism*. New York, NY.
- Lango, J. W. 2014. *The Ethics of Armed Conflict: A Cosmopolitan Just War Theory*. Edinburgh, UK.
- Larson, E. J. 1995. *Sex, Race, and Science: Eugenics in the Deep South*. Baltimore, MD.
- Llompert, J. and Akiba, E. 2006. *Ningen no songen to seimei rinri, seimei hō*. Tokyo.
- Lombardo, P. A. 2008. *Three Generations, No Imbeciles: Eugenics, the Supreme Court, and Buck v. Bell*. Baltimore, MD.
- Lu, S. X. 2019. *The Making of Japanese Settler Colonialism: Malthusianism and Trans-Pacific Migration, 1868-1961*. Cambridge, UK.
- Mackie, V. 2013. *Gender and Modernity in Japan's 'Long Twentieth Century'*, «Journal of Women's History», 25, 3, pp. 62-91.
- Makino, M. 2010. *Hansenbyō no rekishi ni manabu: Hansenbyō ryōyōjo iryō hyakunen wo furikaeru*, in «Nihon Hansenbyō Gakkai Zasshi», vol. 79, no. 1, pp. 25-36.

- Matsubara, Y. 2000. *Nihon: sengo no Yūsei hogo hō toiu na no danshu hō*, in Yonemoto Y., Matsubara Y., Nudeshima J., and Ichinokawa Y. *Yūseigaku to ningen shakai: seimeikagaku no seiki wa doko he mukau noka*. Tokyo.
- Matsubara, Y. 2002. *Kagakushi nyūmon: Yūsei hogo hō no rekishizō no saken-tō*, in «Kagakushi Kenkyū», vol. 41, pp. 104-106.
- Matsubara, Y. 2019. *Hikiagesha iryō kyūgo ni okeru soshikiteki jinkō ninshin chūzetsu: Yūsei hogo hō zenshi*, in Tsuboi H. (ed.), *Jendā to seiseiji: sengo Nihon wo yomikaeru*, vol. 4. Kyoto.
- Meadows, P. 1957. *The Semiotic of Kenneth Burke*, in «Philosophy and Phenomenology Research», vol. 18, no. 1, pp. 80-87.
- Morgan, J. 2019. *Kikuta Noboru and Adoption Law in Japan*, in «Reitaku Daigaku Kiyō», vol. 102, pp. 35-44.
- Morgan, J. 2024. *The Individual in (as) the Body Politic: Seichō no Ie and Anti-Abortion Kokutai Spiritualism in 1960s Japan*, in R. D. Eldridge and Jason Morgan, eds. *Japan in the 1960s: Ten Years of Turning Points*. Oxon, UK.
- Morioka, M. 1995. *Nihon ni okeru feminizumu seimei rinri no keisei katei: 70-80 nendai Yūsei hogo hō kaiaku hantai undō ga teiki suru mono*, in «Seimei Rinri», vol. 5, no. 1, pp. 60-64.
- Morioka, M. 1997. *Yūsei hogo hō kaisei wo meguru seimei rinri*, in «Nihon Kenkyū: Kokusai Nihon Bunka Sentā Kiyō», vol. 16, pp. 211-224.
- Mutsuro, J. 1994. *Hō no naka no danjo fubyōdō: Baishun bōshi hō, Yūsei hogo hō, Kōshitsu tenpan*. Tokyo.
- Nagura, M. 2021. *Seimeikagaku toshite no 'shinka, iden' kyōiku no hitsuyōsei nitsuite ichikōsatsu: sengo chūtō rika kyōiku no hensen oyobi shinkaron, yūseigaku nikansuru jidai shichō yori*, in «Nihon Kagaku Kyōiku Gakkai Dai 45 Nenkai Ronbunshū», pp. 417-420.
- Nakaso, H. 2019. *Kyū Yūsei hogo hō to kenpō 13 jō*, in «Ehime Daigaku Kyōiku Gakubu Kiyō», vol. 66, pp. 113-122.
- Namase, K. 1997. *1970 nendai shoki ni okeru 'Yūsei hogo hō kaiaku soshi' wo meguru ūman ribu undō to shōgaisha mondai nikansuru oboegaki*, in «Momoyama Gakuin Daigaku Kirisutokyō Ronshū», vol. 33, pp. 245-260.
- Ngai, M. M. 1999. *The Architecture of Race in American Immigration Law: A Reexamination of the Immigration Act of 1924*, in «Journal of American History», vol. 86, no. 1, pp. 67-92.
- Nihei, Y. 1949. *Ningen no kaizō*. Tokyo.
- Nishimura, Y. 2024. *Yūsei hogo hō to Hansenbyō: yūsei hogo hō ka de okonawareta Hansenbyō kanja ni taisuru funin shujutsu*, in «Gunma Daigaku Shakai Jōhō Gakubu Kenkyū Ronshū», vol. 31, pp. 49-65.
- Norgren, T. 2001. *Abortion before Birth Control: The Politics of Reproduction in Postwar Japan*. Princeton, NJ.
- Ogawa, S. 1964. *Yūsei hogo hō no mondaiten ni tsuite*, in «Minzoku Eisei», vol. 30, no. 1, pp. 13-26.
- Okada, Y. 2024. *Yūsei hogo hō no jidai wo ikiru: aru seishinkai no sengoshi*. Tokyo.
- Ōkura, K. 1974. *Jinruiidengaku kara mita Yūsei hogo hō no tekiyō nikansuru gigi*, «Nihon Senten Ijō Gakkai Kaihō», 14, 3, pp. 178-179.

- Olson, H., H. Cummings, and J. H. Wigmore. 1924. *The Loeb-Leopold Case (Concluded): A Symposium of Comments from the Legal Profession*, in «Journal of the American Institute of Criminal Law and Criminology», 15, 3, pp. 395-405.
- Oseki, M. 1950. *Yūsei hogo hō to seishinbyō*, in «Sanfujinka no Shinpo», 2, 1, pp. 1-4.
- Otsubo, S. 2018. *Globalizing Reproductive Politics: Sanger's Legacy in Japan*, in «Journal of the Gilded Age and Progressive Era», 17, 4, pp. 728-729.
- Pichot, A., tr. D. Fernbach. 2009. *The Pure Society: From Darwin to Hitler*. New York, NY.
- Rafter, N. 2004. *Earnest A. Hooton and the Biological Tradition in American Criminology*, in «Criminology», 42, 3, pp. 735-771.
- Rashdall, H. 1894. *The Limits of Casuistry*, in «International Journal of Ethics», vol. 4, no. 4, pp. 459-480.
- Rydell, R. W. 2010. *The Proximity of the Past: Eugenics in American Culture*, in «Modern Intellectual History», 7, 3, pp. 667-678.
- Saikō Saibansho. 2024. «Kokka baishō seikyū jiken, 1319, July 3».
- Saikō Saibansho. 2024a. «Kokka baishō seikyū jiken, nos. (o) 1341 and 1682, July 3».
- Saikō Saibansho Jimu Sōkyoku. 2016. «Hansenbyō wo riyū tosuru kaitei basho shitei nikansuru chōsa hōkokusho».
- Saikō Saibansho Jimu Sōkyoku. 2016a. «Yūshikisha iinkai iken». «Hansenbyō wo riyū tosuru kaitei basho shitei nikansuru chōsa hōkokusho (besshi)».
- Sakamoto, S. 2015. *Josei no kenri kara mita dataizai to yūsei hogo hō, soshite botai hogo hō*, in «Higashi Ajia Kenkyū», 63, pp. 33-45.
- Sankei Shimbun. 2016. «Sagamihara shi 19 nin shisatsu jiken wa Nachisu no T4 sakusen datta noka? Yogisha ga kanka sareta Hitorā no yuganda shisō ga himotoku». August 8, 2016.
- Sasatani, E. 2018. *Shinseiji masu sukurīningu dōnyū go no hoinsha kensaku to shushō mae shindan*, in «Ritsumeikan Ningenkagaku Kenkyū», 37, pp. 17-30.
- Sawada, K. 2016. *Shushōryoku to kazoku ni miru Okinawa: shūhenka sareta jinkō, seishoku wo meguru seiji*, in «Shakaigaku Hyōron», 67, 4, pp. 400-414.
- Sekino M. 2016. *Daigokai: Tōkyō saiban kenkyūkai, 'Nihonjin wo kuruwaseta sennō kōsaku "WGIP": sono mokuteki to shisōteki genryū: soshite damasareru Nihonjingawa no yōin to kongo e no kyōkun'*, «Hikaku Hōsei Kenkyū», 39, pp. 163-197.
- Setoguchi, Y. 2012. *Yūsei hogo hō ka de umareta Hansenbyō kanja no kodomotachi: sono jinbutsushiteki kōsatsu no tame no yobiteki kenkyū*, in «Nayoro Shiritsu Daigaku Shakaifukushi Gakka Kenkyū Kiyō», 1, pp. 23-33.
- Shimokawa M. 2017. *Bōkyaku no hikiageshi: Izumi Seiichi to Futsukaichi hoyōjo*. Fukuoka.
- Smith, S. C. 2023. *Buck as (Anti) Canon: The Misuse of Eugenics Rhetoric in Selective-Abortion Jurisprudence and the Dangers for Tort Law*, in «American University Law Review», vol. 73, pp. 449-505.

- Sonoi, Y. 2004. *Yūsei shisō no shakaishi josetsu: Meiji ikō no Nihon shakai wo rei ni*, in «Ningenkagaku Kyōsei Shakaigaku», 4, pp. 43-59.
- Sowa, S. 2010. *Nōmaraizēshon to shakaiteki, kyōikuteki inkurūjon*. Kyoto.
- Stewart, H. L. 1914. *The Need for a Modern Casuistry*, «International Journal of Ethics», 24, 4, pp. 379-401.
- Sueda, K. 2023. *Aichiken ni okeru Yūsei hogo hō ka de no kyōsei funin shujutsu no unyō jittai: 1966 nendo kara – 1971 nendo wo chūshin ni*, in «Aichi Shukutoku Daigaku Ronshū: Fukushi Kōken Gakubu Hen», 13, pp. 19-32.
- Suzuki, H. 2020. *Kyū Yūsei hogo hō ni motozuku kyōsei funin shujutsu to kokusai jinken*, «Kokusai Josei», 34, 1, pp. 139-142.
- Takahashi, S. 2016. *Nihon wo kaitai suru sensō puropaganda no genzai: WGIP no genryū wo saguru*, Tokyo.
- Takahashi, S. 2019. *WGIP to 'rekishisen': 'Nihonjin no dōtoku' wo torimodosu*. Kashiwa, Japan.
- Takara, S. 2021. *Kyū Yūsei hogo hō Sendai chisai hanketsu no kentō*, in «Okinawa Daigaku Jinbun Gakubu Kiyō», 24, pp. 101-108.
- Takayama, Y. and Hamano, Y. 1997. *Josei shōgaisha no genjō to kongo: Yūsei hogo hō kara Botai hogo hō e no ikō no naka de*, «Yokohama Kokuritsu Daigaku Kyōiku Kiyō», 37, pp. 125-133.
- Takeuchi-Demirci, A. 2018. *Contraceptive Diplomacy: Reproductive Politics and Imperial Ambitions in the United States and Japan*, Stanford, CA.
- Taniguchi, Y. and Fukuda M. 1948. *Yūsei hogo hō kaisetsu*. Tokyo.
- Toshimitsu, K. 2019. *Yūsei hogo hō no moto de no kyōsei funin shujutsu to kōbunsho*, «Ritsumeikan Seizongaku Kenkyū», 3, pp. 129-142.
- Tsuge, A. 2019. *Seishoku kanri no sengo: Yūsei hogo hō seiritsu mae no chūzetsu to shutai wo megutte*, in Tsuboi H., ed. *Jendā to seiseiji: sengo Nihon wo yomikaeru*, vol. 4. Kyoto.
- Tsukahara, K. 2014. *Chūzetsu gijutsu to ripurodakutivu raitsu: feminisuto rinri no shiten kara*. Tokyo.
- Tsumagari, Y. 2002. *Ishii Ryōichi*. Tokyo.
- Tsuru, S. 2007. *Mō hitotsu no jinkaku gainen: Revinasu no shisō wo tegakari ni*, in «Hattatsuningengaku Ronsō», 10, pp. 69-75.
- Usui, T. 2019. *Kiroku wo nokoshi, kōkai suru koto no imi: kyū Yūsei hogo hō, Hansenbyō no kiroku wo daizai ni kangaeru*, «Ākaibuzugaku Kenkyū», 31, pp. 31-46.
- von Platz, J. 2016. *Singularity without Equivalence: The Complex Unity of Kant's Categorical Imperative*, in «Journal of Value Inquiry», 50, pp. 369-384.
- Wardle, L. 1993. *'Crying Stones': A Comparison of Abortion in Japan and the United States*, in «New York Law School Journal of International and Comparative Law», 14, 2, pp. 183-259.
- Watanabe, T. 2021. *Kyū Yūsei hogo hō soshō ni okeru kaisei mae minpō 724 jō kōdan no kōka no seigen*, «Seikei Hōgaku», 94, pp. 75-101.
- Yamada, T. 2020. *Kyū Yūsei hogo hō kokubai soshō ni okeru songai oyobi jikō, joseki kikan no kentō*, «Hō to Seiji», 71, 1, pp. 367-454.

- Yamamoto, Y. 2008. *Baishun bōshi hō to bungaku: Kawasaki Chōtarō no baai*, «Shōhoku Kiyō», 29, pp. 109-120.
- Yamashita, U. 1970. *Fukuoka kennai yon chiku ni okeru kazoku keikaku no jittai chōsa (dai nana hō): jinkō ninshin chūzetsu no jitsujō*, «Kaseigaku Zasshi», 21, 1, pp. 75-82.
- Yōda, H. 1999. *Shōgaisha sabetsu no shakaigaku*, Tokyo.
- Yokoyama, T. 2015. *Nihon ga yūsei shakai ni naru made: kagaku keimō, medeia, seishoku no seiji*, Tokyo.
- Yokoyama, T. 2020. *Yūseigakushi ni okeru Nihon minzoku eisei gakkai no ichi*, «Nihon Kenkō Gakkai Shi», 86, 5, pp. 197-208.
- Yokoyama, T. 2021. *Nihon no yūseigakushi kenkyū no korekara wo kangaeru tameni: Sagamihara jiken to Yūsei hogo hō hōdō e no shoken*, «Kagakushi Kenkyū», 60, pp. 66-77.
- Yokozuka K. 2007. *Hahayo! korosuna*, Tokyo.
- Yoshida, K. 2011. *Kikuta ishi jiken to Yūsei hogo hō kaisei mondai: 'umu jiyū' wo megutte*, «Igaku Tetsugaku, Igaku Rinri», 29, pp. 53-62.
- Yoshimura, R. 2023. *'Kyū Yūsei hogo hō soshō' ni okeru minpō 724 jō kōdan (kyū kitei) no tekiyō seigen nikansuru saikin no kakyūshin hanketsu wo dō miruka*, «Ritsumeikan Hōgaku», 411-412, pp. 520-547.
- Yui, H. 2024. *1950 nendai kara 60 nendai Nihon ni okeru kazoku keikaku to yūsei shujutsu: Yūsei hogo hō 3 jō ni motozuku yūsei shujutsu*, «Ritsumeikan Ningenkagaku Kenkyū», 48, pp. 33-46.

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